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Immunomodulatory effects of *Ascaridia galli* excretory-secretory products, including extracellular vesicles, on host immune cell function

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ABSTRACT

Gastrointestinal nematode infections, particularly *Ascaridia galli* (*A. galli*), pose challenges to the poultry industry especially in free-range chickens. These nematodes employ sophisticated immunomodulation strategies to evade host immune defences, allowing them to establish chronic infections. Excretory-secretory (ES) products, including extracellular vesicles (EVs), play a pivotal role in host–parasite communication. Thus, this study aimed to investigate the immunomodulatory properties of nematode-derived ES/EVs, and evaluate the impact of ivermectin (IVM) on these interactions *in vitro*. Adult *A. galli* worms were collected from the jejunum of infected chickens and cultured *in vitro* with or without IVM treatment. ES products were collected, and EVs were enriched using size-exclusion chromatography. T-cell proliferation and macrophage activation assays were performed to assess the immunomodulatory effects of ES/EVs. *A. galli*-derived ES products suppressed T-cell activation (CD25+CD57+ cells) and reduced blast transformation in both CD4+ and CD8+ T-cells ($P < 0.05$). Furthermore, ES promoted TLR4-induced macrophage NO production, changed macrophage-activated surface phenotype, and inhibited macrophage phagocytosis in high concentration but promoted it in low concentration ($P < 0.05$). Additionally, *A. galli*-derived EVs were detected in culture supernatants, and this EV secretion was decreased with the IVM treatment ($P < 0.05$). Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy confirmed IVM treatment altered EV cargo composition. Finally, the EVs influenced cytokine profiles of activated macrophages, decreasing pro-inflammatory cytokine gene expression (IL-1 β and IL-8, $P < 0.05$) which may mirror immune evasion *in vivo*. In summary, this study highlights immunomodulatory mechanisms of *A. galli* ES/EVs and provides fundamental information for developing diagnostic and therapeutic strategies targeting nematode ES products including EVs.

RESEARCH HIGHLIGHTS

- Excretory-secretory (ES) products, including extracellular vesicles (EVs), demonstrated immunomodulatory properties.
- *A. galli* ES suppressed T-cell activation, proliferation, and macrophage phagocytosis.
- *A. galli* ES, including EVs, may help in evading the host immune system.

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Introduction

Gastrointestinal (GI) infections with helminths threaten the global livestock industries, causing substantial economic losses, affecting food security, and causing welfare problems for the animals. Parasitic worms infect a wide range of hosts, including livestock, leading to reduced productivity, increased morbidity, and mortality (Hamid *et al.*, 2023). The poultry industry is particularly vulnerable to nematode infections, made worse by the increasing popularity of free-range and organic farming systems, which provide ideal conditions for their spread. In the poultry industry, *Ascaridia galli* (*A. galli*) has been identified as the most prevalent GI nematode infection causing Ascariidiosis. This parasite predominantly inhabits the small intestine, where it affects the intestinal epithelium, leading to malabsorption, weight loss, decreased egg production, and increased mortality rates. These impacts collectively contribute to significant annual economic losses (Pleidrup *et al.*, 2014; Shifaw *et al.*, 2021).

Helminth infections involve complex interactions between the parasite and the host immune system. These interactions are well described for mammals but large knowledge gaps exist concerning helminth infections in chickens. Hence, in mammals, the worms employ sophisticated strategies to evade and manipulate the host immune defences, allowing them to persist, replicate, and establish chronic infections. In particular, immunomodulation is a key strategy to alter and suppress the host immune responses to avoid detection and clearance by the host immune systems (Cooper & Eleftherianos, 2016). Helminths modulate immune responses at multiple stages, disrupting innate antigen recognition, impairing adaptive immunity activation, and hindering the deployment of effector mechanisms (McSorley *et al.*, 2013). As reviewed by White, McManus *et al.* (2020a), helminths can potentially use the regulatory T-cell (Treg) pathways of the host to manipulate the host immune system. A crucial component of this strategy involves the release of excretory-secretory (ES) products, which include biomolecules such as lipids, glycans, and small molecules. These ES products are believed to initiate early communication with the host, altering immune responses to facilitate invasion and persistence (Drurey & Maizels, 2021). For instance, Bancroft and Grecnis (2021) highlighted that ES products from *Trichuris muris* nematodes can suppress pro-inflammatory cytokine production by host macrophages. Similarly, leucyl aminopeptidase (ES-62), found in ES products secreted by the adult worm *Acanthocheilonema viteae*, has been shown to inhibit the activation and proliferation of host T-cells (Hewitson *et al.*, 2009). Among the components of nematode ES products, extracellular vesicles (EVs) have emerged as pivotal mediators of host–pathogen

communication (Rooney *et al.*, 2022). EVs are nanoscale, lipid-bilayer-enclosed vesicles secreted by all living cells, carrying a diverse cargo of bioactive molecules such as proteins, lipids, and RNA (Welsh *et al.*, 2024). Previous studies have demonstrated that cargo molecules associated with helminth-derived EVs play a crucial role in modulating the host immune system. Most importantly, these EV-mediated communications can impact immune cells by delivering their cargo molecules to specific targeted cells selectively (Drurey & Maizels, 2021). EVs derived from *Heligmosomoides polygyrus* and *T. muris* nematodes have been found to carry miRNAs that suppress host inflammatory responses by targeting specific signalling pathways (White, Kumar *et al.*, 2020b). Similarly, a study by Ilić *et al.* (2021) demonstrated that EVs from the nematode *Trichinella spiralis* deliver immunomodulatory proteins to host cells, altering their function and promoting an anti-inflammatory phenotype. The ability of EVs to cross biological barriers and deliver their cargo to distant cells makes them highly effective tools for manipulating host immunity. While increasing evidence underscores the importance of nematode-derived EVs in host–pathogen interactions, their role in avian nematode infections remains largely uninvestigated.

Ivermectin (IVM) is a widely used anthelmintic medication in both human and veterinary medicine, demonstrating strong efficacy against a broad range of parasitic diseases, including GI parasites (Laing *et al.*, 2017). As of today, no vaccine has been developed for *A. galli* infections, and, as a result, controlling this infection primarily relies on prophylactic therapy with anthelmintic drugs. Previous studies have highlighted the potential of using IVM as an effective treatment for controlling *A. galli* infections in chickens (Ritu *et al.*, 2024). However, IVM is not approved for use as an anthelmintic drug in commercial chickens in many countries, including the USA and EU (Goetting *et al.*, 2011). Interestingly, research by Loghry *et al.* (2020) revealed that therapeutically relevant concentrations of IVM suppress the secretion of EVs in various parasitic nematodes, but do not impair their motility (Loghry *et al.*, 2020). This suggests that IVM may disrupt nematode–host communication and weaken the ability of parasites to modulate host immunity by inhibiting EV secretion. However, the specific effects of IVM on the secretion and immunomodulatory properties of ES products and EVs from *A. galli* have not been explored.

The knowledge gap in nematodes and early host–pathogen communications presents a significant opportunity to explore the potential mechanisms by which ES and EVs influence immune responses in avian hosts. In this study, we aimed to investigate the immunomodulatory effects of *A. galli*-derived ES products and EVs on avian immune cells *in vitro*.

Additionally, the potential of IVM to interfere with these immunomodulatory mechanisms was evaluated. Moreover, by improving our understanding of the interactions between *A. galli* and the avian immune system, this study may contribute to the development of targeted strategies for managing parasitic infections in poultry.

Materials and methods

Birds and ethical clearance

Chickens from line 133 housed at the Department of Animal and Veterinary Sciences, Aarhus University were used. Line 133 is an inbred line of White Leghorn origin containing birds with the MHC haplotype B13 (Miller *et al.*, 2004). All chickens used in the experiment were produced from MHC characterized parents and the MHC haplotypes of the offspring were confirmed by genotyping the LEI0258 microsatellite locus (McConnell *et al.*, 1999) by PCR-based fragment analysis as described earlier (Dalgaard *et al.*, 2005). Ten chickens were infected with 750 embryonated *A. galli* eggs/bird at 7 days of age using a plastic pipette. *A. galli* eggs used for the infection were from female worm uteri obtained from naturally infected commercial hens and embryonated in H₂SO₄ as described earlier (Permin *et al.*, 1997). Water and commercial chicken feed were supplied *ad libitum*. The lighting period was 12 h daily, and the chickens were housed at 21°C temperature.

The experiments involving animal were conducted according to Danish legislation governing bird experimentation (Law no. 382, 10 June 1987; Acts 739, 6 December 1988; and Act 333, 19 May 1990) and were approved by the Danish Animal Experiments Inspectorate (Animal license no. 2022-15-0201-01222).

In vitro culture of *A. galli* nematodes

A. galli-infected chickens were euthanized 10 weeks post-infection and adult worms were collected into a 0.9% NaCl solution. Live worms were maintained at room temperature and transported to the laboratory where they were washed three times thoroughly with room temperature washing medium (Roswell Park Memorial Institute medium (RPMI)-1640 medium with GlutaMAX (Gibco™, Life Technologies Limited, Paisley, UK), supplemented with 100 U/ml penicillin, 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Gibco™) and divided into female and male batches. Worms were placed in T75 culture flasks at a density of 20 worms per 30 ml of RPMI medium supplemented with 1× Antibiotic Antimycotic Solution (Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis, MO, USA, A5955, final concentration of 100 U/ml penicillin, 100 µg/ml streptomycin, 250 ng/ml

amphotericin B). RPMI was chosen as the culture medium based on reports of superior worm viability as compared to other culture media (Ritu *et al.*, 2024). Additional female worm cultures were prepared with or without 1 µM IVM (Sigma-Aldrich). The IVM concentration was chosen based on previous studies of ivermectin impact on EV secretion from other nematodes (Loghry *et al.*, 2020) and the low worm toxicity reported for this dose (Ritu *et al.*, 2024). The spent medium/ES was collected after 24 h and used fresh for functional cell studies or frozen at –80 until further processing and EV enrichment.

Enrichment of EVs

EVs were enriched using a protocol described previously with minor modifications (Mousavi *et al.*, 2024). In brief, spent medium/ES was first centrifuged at 300× *g* for 10 min at 4°C to remove the nematode eggs, followed by three successive centrifugation steps (400×, 4000×, and 10,000× *g* for 10 min) to remove cells and cell debris. The collected supernatant was filtered through a polyethersulfone 0.45 µm filter (Minisart, Gottingen, Germany) and concentrated to 500 µl with Amicon Ultra-15 centrifugal filter devices with 10 kDa cutoff (MerkMillipore, Darmstadt, Germany). The EVs were enriched from the concentrated supernatant using size exclusion chromatography (SEC) in a cross-linked 4% agarose matrix of 90 µm beads (Sephacrose 4 Fast Flow, GE HealthCare Bio-Sciences AB, Uppsala, Sweden) in a 10 cm gravity column calibrated with PBS. The elute was collected into 20 fractions each containing 500 µl. The fractions 5–7 with high EV numbers and less soluble protein were selected based on the nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA) data and Bradford assay. These fractions were pooled and concentrated to 500 µl and again nanoparticles were analysed using NTA.

EV characterization

Nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA)

Concentrations and sizes of nanoparticles in each fraction were measured with NTA (ZetaView® PMX 110 V3.0 instrument by Particle Metrix GmbH, Inning am Ammersee, Germany, software version 8.05.14 SP7) coupled with ZetaView® NTA software for data analysis. The operating instructions of the manufacturer were followed as described in the literature (Disanayake *et al.*, 2021). The auto-alignment of the instrument was performed using 100 nm polystyrene particle size standards (Applied Microspheres B.V., Leusden, Netherlands). The samples were measured in the scatter mode for estimation of the total particle concentration and size profiles using the following settings: camera sensitivity 85, shutter 70, frame rate 30

frames per second (fps), number of cycles 3, and number of frames 11.

Protein quantification

The Bradford assay was used to determine the soluble contaminating protein concentrations of eluted fractions as described previously (Premathilaka *et al.*, 2025). A dilution series of bovine serum albumin (BSA) (1.4, 1.0, 0.5, 0.25, and 0.125 mg/ml) was prepared from a standard BSA solution (2 mg/ml, Sigma-Aldrich). PBS was used as a negative control. Subsequently, three replicates of each sample, standards, and negative controls of 5 μ l were added to a 96-well microplate. Following this, 95 μ l of Bradford Reagent (Sigma-Aldrich) was added to each well. The microplate was covered and kept on a shaker for 30 s for homogenous mixing. Then, the microplate was incubated at room temperature for 15–30 min. Finally, the absorbance was measured with a spectrophotometer (Ledetect 96 Microplate Reader; Biomed Dr. Wieser GmbH, Salzburg, Austria) at 620 nm wavelength and the protein concentrations of each of the fractions were calculated.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

Morphological evaluation of EVs was carried out using TEM as described elsewhere (Premathilaka *et al.*, 2025). First, 20 μ l of EV suspension was placed on formvar/carbon-coated 200 mesh grids (Agar Scientific, Stansted, UK) and allowed to adsorb on the grid for 20 min. Then the grids were incubated with 2% uranyl acetate (Polysciences, Warrington, PA, USA) for 5 min and air-dried to obtain contrasted images of EVs. The EVs were visualized using the JEM 1400 TEM (JEOL Ltd., Tokyo, Japan, with Morada TEM CCD camera, Olympus, Hamburg, Germany) at 80 kV. The digital images of EV were captured using a numeric camera (Morada TEM CCD camera).

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

The metabolic fingerprints of EVs collected from worms, which were cultured with and without IVM were analysed using Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. Purified EVs from *A. galli* culture supernatants were dried on silicon optical microtitre plates at 40°C for 40 min and analysed in transmission mode using an HTS-XT microplate adapter on a Tensor 27 FTIR spectrometer (Bruker Optics GmbH, Ettlingen, Germany). Spectra were recorded across 4000–500 cm^{-1} with a resolution of 6 cm^{-1} , averaging 32 interferograms per spectrum.

Each spectrum was processed including vector normalization, baseline correction, and second-derivative calculations using a nine-point Savitzky–Golay algorithm (five smoothing points, 3rd-degree polynomial). Spectroscopic ratios of fatty acids (3500–2800 cm^{-1}), proteins (1720–1500 cm^{-1}), and polysaccharides

(1200–900 cm^{-1}) were computed with slight modifications to established methods (Wong *et al.*, 2022; Buchacher *et al.*, 2023). Smoothed and baseline-corrected spectra were integrated, and statistical analysis was performed using ANOVA ($*P < 0.05$). Experiments were conducted in triplicate, with three biological and technical replicates each.

T-cell assay

Isolation of peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC)

Blood samples were obtained from the jugular vein and collected into Vacuette® tubes coated with 18 IU/ml sodium heparin (Greiner Bio-One, Stonehouse, ULK). Four ml of peripheral blood from each bird (adult White Leghorn hens) were diluted with an equal amount of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4). Diluted blood was carefully layered onto Ficoll-Paque® reagent (Cytiva, Marlborough, MA, USA) in two 15 ml polypropylene tubes which were centrifuged 400 \times g for 25 min 20°C (acceleration 5, brake 1). Following centrifugation, the interphase and everything above it was transferred to a new 15 ml tube containing 10 ml of PBS centrifuged 300 \times g for 10 min followed by two additional washes with PBS. After discarding the supernatant, cells were resuspended in RPMI-1640 medium containing 25 mM HEPES and 300 mg/l L-glutamine (Lonza, Basel, Switzerland) supplemented with 10% foetal bovine serum (FBS, Gibco, Invitrogen Corp., Carlsbad, CA, USA) at a concentration of 2×10^7 cells/ml.

T-cell proliferation/activation

Mitogen stimulation was performed as described by (Naghizadeh *et al.*, 2022) with a few modifications. The PBMCs (1×10^6 cells/well) were stimulated in 96-well plates (Nunclon Delta Surface plates, Thermo-scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) with a final concentration of 10 μ g/ml concanavalin A (ConA, Sigma) and various dilutions of spent medium/ES (3-fold dilutions, 1:6–1:1458). Initially, the ES dilution 1:2 was also included in the assay, but it had to be omitted from the dataset as cell viability was affected.

The samples were incubated for 5 min on a shaker at room temperature and afterwards incubated at 41°C, 5% CO₂ for 72 h. After incubation, cells were treated with a final concentration of 2 mM EDTA at room temperature followed by mixing using pipetting. Cells were pelleted by centrifugation at 600 \times g for 5 min before performing staining for flow cytometric analysis. Labelling was conducted following a protocol previously described by Naghizadeh *et al.* (2022). Cells were stained in 96-well plates by adding FACS buffer (0.2% bovine serum albumin, Sigma, 0.2% sodium azide-Sigma, 0.05% normal horse serum, Gibco) containing anti-CD8 α -FITC (Southern Biotech,

Birmingham, AL, USA), anti-TCR1-PE (Southern Biotech), anti-CD25-PerCp-Cy5.5 (Biorad, Watford, UK, labelled with fluorochrome using the Lightning-Link® kit from Abcam, Cambridge, UK), anti-CD4 pBlue (Southern Biotech) and anti CD57-APC (BD Biosciences, San Jose, CA, USA). The fixable LIVE/DEAD® near-IR fluorescent amine reactive dye (Invitrogen-Molecular Probes, Eugene, USA, L10119) was included as a viability reporter. Staining was performed for 15 min at room temperature followed by washing three times using 200 µl FACS buffer before flow cytometry acquisition.

Flow cytometry was carried out using a BD FACS-Celesta (BD Biosciences) equipped with 488 nm blue, 633 nm red, and 405 nm violet lasers, with data analysed using the FACSDiva (BD Biosciences) software. The assays included single-stained compensation controls and fluorescence minus one (FMO) negative control, with gating strategies illustrated in supplementary Figure 1A.

HD11 cell assays

Cell culture

The chicken macrophage-like cell line HD11, transformed by the avian leukaemia virus strain MC29 (Beug *et al.*, 1979), was maintained in RPMI-1640 containing 25 mM HEPES and 300 mg/l L-glutamine (Lonza), supplemented with 10% FBS and antibiotics (10,000 U/ml penicillin and streptomycin; Lonza), at 41°C, 5% CO₂, and 95% humidity. The cells were detached using trypsin/EDTA (Lonza), harvested and washed with PBS (Lonza). Aliquots of cell suspensions (80,000 cells/50 µl) were seeded into 96-well culture plates (Thermo Fisher Scientific) and cultured in RPMI-1640 (Lonza) supplemented with 10% FBS but without antibiotics. A single batch of FBS was used in all experiments.

LPS stimulation

Cells in 96-well plates were allowed to rest for 5 h before treatment with various dilutions of either spent medium/ES (3-fold dilutions, 1:6–1:1458) or purified EVs (3-fold dilutions, 4–2168 particles per macrophage) for 30 min. Next, cells were stimulated with lipopolysaccharide (LPS, Sigma-Aldrich) at a final concentration of 0.5 µg/ml and incubated at 41°C, 5% CO₂ for 18 h before harvesting 100 µl of the cell culture supernatant which was kept at –20°C for later nitric oxide (NO) analysis. Then the cells were washed twice with PBS and detached using 5 µM EDTA, followed by washing twice with PBS by centrifugation at 200× g for 5 min before resuspension in 100 µl PBS and staining with anti-chicken MHC-II FITC (Southern Biotech) and anti-chicken Kul-01 AF647 (Southern Biotech), both diluted 1:500, for 15 min at 4°C and then subjected to flow cytometric

analysis. The gating strategy is shown in supplementary Figure 1B. Identically plated cells were likewise treated with purified EV and LPS for 18 h and washed twice with PBS before adding 150 µl of RTL buffer (From RNeasy Plus Micro Kit, Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) to each well and the plates were frozen at –80°C for later RNA isolation.

Griess assay to measure nitric oxide production

The nitric oxide production by the HD11 cells was measured by the Griess assay as described elsewhere (Hong *et al.*, 2010). In brief, dilution of the standard stock in PBS was added to the 96-well plate as a standard series. The samples were diluted in PBS, and 100 µl of each sample was added to each well. Griess reagent (50 µl of 1% sulphanilamide and 50 µl of 0.1% naphthalene diamine, both in a phosphorus acid solution (H₃PO₄) (Sigma-Aldrich)) was added to the plate and incubated for 10 min at room temperature in order to let the Griess reagent turn purple upon reaction with nitrite ions in the cell culture supernatant. The optical density (OD) at 540 nm was measured using a microplate absorbance reader (Multiskan FC, Thermo Fisher) to determine the nitrite concentration of each sample according to the standard curve (sodium nitrite 0.3–100 µM).

Phagocytosis

Aliquots of cell suspensions (80,000 cells/50 µl) were seeded into 96-well culture plates (Thermo Fisher Scientific) and cultured in RPMI-1640 (Lonza) supplemented with 10% FBS but without antibiotics, as described above. Cells were grown for 18 h at 41°C, 5% CO₂ to reach near to 100% confluence and the culture medium was replaced with 100 µl RPMI with various dilutions of spent medium/ES (3-fold dilutions, 1:6–1:1458) and 25 µl of fluorescent *Salmonella* targets. The in-house prepared FITC-labeled heat-killed *S. Infantis* bacteria (JEO1965 (S123443) (Ulrich-Lynge *et al.*, 2015)), were pre-opsonized with 25% chicken serum (Sigma-Aldrich, Life Science) in RPMI for 30 min at room temperature before adding. The plate was then incubated at 41°C, 5% CO₂ for 60 min. Phagocytosis was stopped by removing the supernatant and washing the plate three times with 200 µl PBS. After the final wash, 150 µl of PBS was added, and the cells were harvested by adding EDTA at a final concentration of 5 mM. Finally, paraformaldehyde (PFA, Thermo Fisher Scientific) was added to a final concentration of 1% and flow cytometry was performed after a minimum fixation time of 15 min. Phagocytic activity was determined by flow cytometry using a BD FACSCelesta™. Data analysis was done in the FACSDiva software. Phagocytic activity was expressed as the percentage of cells containing fluorescent beads, designated FITC HD11 cells (%). Mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) was also recorded;

according to the extent of phagocytosis, it reflected the mean number of ingested beads per phagocyte. Gating strategy is shown in supplementary Figure 1C.

Cytokine RT-qPCR

RNA extraction of EV-treated HD11 cells was done using the RNeasy Plus Micro kit (Qiagen). Residual genomic DNA contamination was removed using the spin columns included in the kit. RNA concentration of each sample was measured using a NanoDrop® ND-1000 Spectrophotometer and was afterward diluted to 10 ng/ml using DEPC treated water (Invitrogen). Reverse transcription of RNA to cDNA was done using the High-Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription Kit (Applied Biosystems, Carlsbad, CA, USA). RNA was mixed 1:1 with a master mix in PCR tubes and placed in a thermal cycler (Swift MaxPro, Esco Healthcare, Singapore) at 25°C for 10 min, 37°C for 120 min, and 85°C for 5 min. Samples were then stored at -20°C until further use. Each qPCR reaction consisted of 8 µl of reaction mix (SsoAdvanced™ Universal SYBR® Green Supermix, Bio-Rad) containing 0.25 µM of both forward and reverse primers, and 2 µl of cDNA. Primer sequences are shown in Table 1. The stability of HPRT-1, HMBS, GAPDH, RLP-13 and TBP as reference genes was evaluated based on their expression on both LPS-treated and untreated cells. HMBS was found to be the most stably expressed and was used as a normalization factor during calculations. Samples were loaded on a 384-well plate (Applied Biosystems) and placed in a ViiA7™ qPCR system, using a two-step PCR protocol as follows: hold stage at 95°C for 20 s (ramp rate 1.9°C/s); PCR stage with 40 cycles at 95°C for 1 s followed by 60°C for 20 s (ramp rate 1.6°C/s) with optics on; and melt curve stage for 15 s at 95°C (1.9°C/s), 60°C for 1 min, and 95°C for 15 s (ramp rate 0.05°C/s) with optics on. Expression of target genes was calculated using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$ method.

Presence of non-*A. galli* products in ES and EV samples

Mycoplasma detection

The presence of mycoplasma in EVs and ES was determined using the LookOut® Mycoplasma PCR Detection Kit (Sigma-Aldrich). The PCR master mix was prepared using 22.5 µl of rehydration buffer included in the kit and 1.25 U of JumpStart™ Taq DNA Polymerase (Sigma-Aldrich) for each sample. Twenty-three µl of the PCR master mix was added to each test tube included in the kit followed by 2 µl of sample in each sample tube and 2 µl of DEPC-treated water (Invitrogen) in the negative control tube. Lastly, 25 µl of the master mix was added to the positive control tube supplied with the kit. After a 5 min incubation at room temperature, all tubes were transferred to a

thermal cycler for PCR amplification with the following programme: 1 cycle of 94°C for 2 min and 40 cycles of 94°C for 30 s, 55°C for 30 s, 72°C for 40 s and then cooled to 4°C. Results were visualized using electrophoresis by loading 8 µl of PCR product on a 1.5% agarose gel (Lonza). No mycoplasma was detected in either ES or EV samples by this method (data not shown). These results were also confirmed by a missing mycoplasma signature in the FTIR spectrum of the EV samples.

Endotoxin detection

To determine the amount of endotoxin in the samples the Pierce™ Chromogenic Endotoxin Quant Kit (Thermo Scientific) was used following the manufacturer's instructions. A standard curve was used for the quantification of endotoxin by making a 2-fold dilution series, using endotoxin-free water included in the kit, of a known standard (*E. coli*) starting with 1 EU/ml until four dilutions were made (1, 0.5, 0.25 and 0.1 EU/ml). Samples were diluted 1:20 in endotoxin-free water, and 50 µl of samples, standards, and blanks were loaded in duplicates in a Maxisorp 96-well micro-titre plate inside an incubator at 37°C. Maintaining the plate at 37°C throughout the procedure, 50 µl of reconstituted lyophilized amebocyte lysate was added to each well and incubated for 12 min. After 12 min, 100 µl of reconstituted lyophilized chromogenic substrate was added to each well for 6 min. After the reaction was stopped with 50 µl of 25% acetic acid, the absorbance at 405 nm was read immediately afterwards in an ELISA plate reader (Multiskan FC, Thermo Fisher). Endotoxin contamination was determined to be in the range of 18.8–22 EU. In the functional assays ES/EV was further diluted between 1:6 and 1:1458 which corresponds to a maximum LPS contamination of 3.1–7.3 EU or 0.5–1 ng/ml, which is negligible to the LPS activation dose of 0.5 µg/ml used for macrophage activation.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis of NTA measurements was performed using R studio (R-4.1.2) and the data are presented as mean ± standard error of the mean (SEM). The differences between EV concentration and average particle size were assessed with two-way ANOVA with *post-hoc* Tukey multiple comparison tests for intergroup comparisons. All flow cytometry and qPCR data were analysed in R (v.4.4.0) using a linear model with the different concentrations of ES and EVs as the independent variable. Differences in the responses between the various concentrations of ES and EVs for samples treated with or without IVM, and the controls, were determined by one-way ANOVA and multiple comparison tests adjusted by the Tukey method. A *P*-value lower than 0.05 was

Table 1. Sequences of primers used in RT-qPCR.

Sequence (5'–3')	Symbol	Gene	Accession no.
F: GGTTGAGATGCTCCGTGAGTTT R: GGCTCTTCTCCCAATCTTAGAA	HMBS	Hydroxymethylbilane synthase	>XM_040690599.2
F: TGGGCATCAAGGGCTACA R: TCGGGTTGGTTGGTGATG	IL-1 β	Interleukin-1 β	>NM_204524.2
F: CCAAGCACACCTCTCTTCCA R: GCAAGGTAGGACGCTGGTAA	IL-8	Interleukin 8	>NM_205498.2
F: GCTGAGGGTGAAGTTGAGGA R: TCTGTGTAGAAGCGCAGCAT	IL-10	Interleukin 10	>NM_001004414.4
F: AGATGCTGGCAACTACACCTG R: CATTGCCCCATTGGAGTCTAC	IL-12p40	Interleukin 12p40	>NM_213571.2
F: GGCAGCAGCGTCTCTATGACTTG R: GACTTTAGGCTGCCAGGTTG	iNOS	Inducible nitric oxide synthase	>NM_204961.2

considered statistically significant. Results for flow cytometry are shown as mean \pm SE. For qPCR data, results are shown as fold changes compared to samples treated only with LPS and without EV treatment.

Results

Immunomodulatory effects of spent media from nematode cultures on T-cell activation

The surface markers of activated and proliferating T-cells were analysed using flow cytometry. The study analysed the proportions of T-cell subsets expressing the activation markers CD25, CD57, and undergoing blast transformation across different dilutions of nematode culture supernatants, treated with or without IVM (Figure 1). The frequencies of CD4 markers, including CD25+, CD57+, and blasts showed a dose-dependent reduction when treated with increased amounts of ES (Figure 1(A,C,E)) from both IVM (+) and IVM (–) nematode culture supernatants. However, the reduction as compared to controls without ES was only statistically significant in the highest ES concentrations. A significant reduction in frequency of CD4+ cells expressing CD25 was observed in the IVM (–) group at the highest concentration (6 \times dilution) compared to the IVM (–) control ($P = 0.0017$) (Figure 1(A)). A significant reduction in the frequency of CD4+ cells expressing CD57 was observed in the IVM (–) group at high concentrations (6 \times and 18 \times dilutions) ($P = 0.0215$ and 0.0177 , respectively) (Figure 1(C)). Finally, a significant decrement of CD4+ blast formation was observed at the high concentrations of IVM (–) groups ($P = 0.0005$ and 0.001 respectively) (Figure 1(E)). For the CD4+ cells, no statistically significant effect of +/- IVM was observed for any of the parameters except for the no-EV controls where ConA-induced blastogenesis was higher in cells kept in medium without IVM as compared to medium including IVM ($P = 0.03$) (Figure 1(E)). For CD8+ T-cells, similar dose-dependent reductions in CD25+ and blast frequencies were observed by increased ES concentration (Figure 1(B,F)). Interestingly, the profile of CD57+ frequencies were bell formed and, after initial reduction,

showed higher CD57+ frequencies at high ES concentration (Figure 1(D)). The frequency of CD8+ cells expressing CD25 was significantly reduced in the IVM (–) group at the highest concentration (6 \times dilution) ($P < 0.0001$) (Figure 1(B)). The frequency of CD8+ cells expressing CD57 was significantly increased in the IVM (–) group at the 6 \times dilution ($P = 0.0181$) (Figure 1(D)). Blast formation in CD8+ T-cells was significantly reduced in both the IVM (–) and IVM (+) groups (Figure 1(F)), and this decrement was significant at the highest concentration (6 \times dilution) ($P = 0.0103$ and 0.0024) of both groups. For the CD8+ cells, no statistically significant effect of +/- IVM was observed for any of the parameters.

Immunomodulatory effects of spent media from nematode cultures on HD11 macrophage-like cells

We investigated the effects of spent media from nematode cultures treated with IVM (+) or without (IVM (–)) ivermectin on various immunological parameters of HD11 macrophage-like cells upon TLR4 ligand-induced activation or in the presence of bacterial phagocytosis targets (Figure 2). Following treatment with ES at different dilutions in combination with LPS stimulation, nitric oxide (NO) Production and mannose receptor C-type 1-like b (MRC1L-b) surface expression showed a dose-dependent increase with the increasing ES concentrations in macrophages treated with both IVM (+) and IVM ES samples compared to the control without ES (Figure 2(A,B)). At the highest EV concentration (1:18 dilution), the observed increased NO production was significantly higher for culture supernatant without IVM as compared to culture supernatant with IVM ($P = 0.02$) (Figure 2(A)). The major histocompatibility complex Class II (MHC-II) expression was significantly suppressed in the cells treated with both IVM (+) and IVM (–) ES ($P < 0.05$) for all dilutions. This decrement corresponded with the increment of the concentration of ES (Figure 2(C)). The percentage of phagocytosing macrophages and the number of phagocytosed bacteria were also assessed (Figure 2(D,E)). At higher ES concentrations, both parameters were

Figure 1. The activation and proliferation of T-cells upon stimulation with 10 µg/ml ConA for 72 h and in the presence of *A. galli* nematode culture supernatant containing excretory/secretory products. Proportions: (A) CD25+ of CD4+ T-cells, (B) CD25+ of CD8+ T-cells, (C) CD57+ of CD4+ T-cells, (D) CD57+ of CD8+ T-cells, (E) blast of CD4+ T-cells, (F) blast of CD8+ T-cells. Mean ± standard error, * = $P < 0.05$ IVM (-) groups compared to their control group, and # = $P < 0.05$ IVM (+) groups compared to their control group.

significantly reduced in the IVM (+) and IVM (-) groups compared to the controls ($P < 0.05$). However, at lower ES concentrations, the IVM (+) group

displayed a significant increment in both phagocytosis and MFI ($P < 0.05$). For both parameters, there was a tendency that phagocytosis was higher in the presence

Figure 2. LPS-induced activation and phagocytic potential of HD11 cells in the presence of *A. galli* nematode culture supernatant containing excretory/secretory products. (A) NO production from LPS-activated macrophages, (B) mannose receptor C-type 1-like b (MRC1L-B) surface expression on LPS-activated macrophages indicated as mean fluorescence intensity (MFI), (C) MHC-II surface expression on LPS-activated macrophages indicated as MFI, (D) percentage of phagocytosing macrophages, (E) number of phagocytosed bacteria per macrophage indicated as MFI. (Mean \pm standard error, * = $P < 0.05$ IVM (-) groups compared to their control group, and # = $P < 0.05$ IVM (+) groups compared to their control group.

of culture supernatants prepared with IVM as compared to culture supernatants without IVM. This observation was, however, only statistically significant for the percentage of phagocytosing cells in the presence of culture supernatant diluted 162 times ($P = 0.02$) (Figure 2(D)) and for the number of phagocytosed bacteria in the presence of culture supernatant diluted 18, 54, and 162 times ($P = 0.03$, $P = 0.01$, $P = 0.02$, respectively).

Analysis of EV enrichment from ES and their characterization

Eluted fractions from SEC were subjected to NTA analysis and results revealed that fractions 5–7 were enriched with nanoparticles (Figure 3(A)). According to the protein assay results, minimal or no soluble proteins were detected in EV-enriched fractions. Additionally, the average concentration and size of the particles were 1.36×10^{10} particles/ml and 168.77 nm respectively (Figure 3(B,C)). The size distribution of the enriched nanoparticles was in the

range from 50–370 nm (Figure 3(D)). TEM analysis of enriched nanoparticles confirmed the presence of EVs by indicating the characteristic shape of EVs. The clear background in the TEM image suggested that the enriched EVs were minimally contaminated with artefacts (Figure 3(E)). EVs enriched from nematode culture treated with IVM (IVM (+)) showed a significant reduction of total particle concentration compared to the non-treated group ($P = 0.02$) (Figure 4(A)). However, there was no significant difference in the average particle size between the two groups (Figure 4(B)).

Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy for nematode EV characterization

Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was employed to characterize EVs enriched from adult *A. galli* worms, both IVM (–) and IVM (+), to analyse their basic metabolomic composition (Figure 5). Spectral data for EVs were recorded in the range of

Figure 3. Physical characterization of nematode-derived extracellular vesicles (EVs). EVs were enriched from *A. galli* cultured spent medium by size exclusion chromatography coupled with sequential centrifugation. (A) elution profile of nanoparticles, and the red line indicates soluble protein concentration in EV enriched fractions, (B) total nanoparticle concentration, (C) average nanoparticle size, (D) size distribution profile of nanoparticles, (E) TEM image of EVs indicating the typical shapes with clear background. The data are presented as the mean \pm SEM.

Figure 4. Characteristic comparison of enriched EVs from IVM-treated and non-treated *A. galli* cultures. (A) total nanoparticle concentration, (B) average nanoparticle size. The data are presented as the mean \pm SEM (*, $P < 0.05$).

Figure 5. Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy of EVs shed from *A. galli* without (IVM (-), blue) and with added IVM (IVM (+), red), three technical replicates by biological replicate. (A) total absorbance spectra, (B) zoom-in into the region characteristic for proteins, (C) zoom-in into the region characteristic for polysaccharides, (D) subtraction spectral analysis of the second derivative showing the most prevalent differences between IVM (-) and IVM (+) samples (purple), (E) zoom-in of the subtraction spectral analysis characteristic for proteins, (F) zoom-in of the subtraction spectral analysis characteristic for polysaccharides.

4000–500 cm^{-1} to investigate the molecular cargo associated with each experimental condition. Subtraction analysis of second-derivative spectra revealed distinct differences in the EV cargo between IVM (–) and IMV (+) samples.

The most notable variations were observed in the protein region (1700–1500 cm^{-1} , Figure 5(A)), where a detailed examination indicated a shift in the C=O stretching vibrations, characteristic of amides. Specifically, absorption bands corresponding to the amide I (1650 cm^{-1}) and amide II (1545 cm^{-1}) groups demonstrated the high protein content in the EVs (Figure 5(B)). The amide I peak arises primarily from the C=O stretching of peptide bonds in proteins, while the amide II peak is attributed to the coupling of N–H bending and C–N stretching vibrations, highlighting the protein backbone differences between treated and untreated worms (Figure 5(C)).

In addition, significant differences were observed in the subtraction spectra for both protein and polysaccharide regions (Figure 5(D)). The spectroscopic profiles of protein cargo differed between the IVM (+) and IVM (–) groups, indicating substantial alterations in EV-associated proteins (Figure 5(E)). Similarly, differences between IVM (+) and IVM (–) could be shown in the polysaccharide region; however, the subtraction showed that differences are not as great (Figure 5(F)).

Immunomodulatory effects of EVs from nematode cultures on HD11 macrophage-like cells

We assessed the expression of selected cytokines in LPS-activated macrophage cultures treated with EVs enriched from IVM (+) and IVM (–) spent media. Cytokine mRNA levels were quantified by RT-qPCR, with results presented as fold changes compared to the control (Figure 6). A significant increment in IL-10 expression was observed in macrophages treated with higher particle/EV numbers ($P < 0.05$) (Figure 6(A,B)) but the dose-dependent response appeared to be more profound in the presence of IVM (–) EVs (Figure 6(A)). Production of iNOS and IL-1 β expression was significantly increased as a response to the increment of particle number in both IVM (–) and IVM (+) groups ($P < 0.05$) (Figure 6(C,D,E,F)). Additionally, IL-8 expression was significantly increased in the IVM (–) group ($P = 0.0311$ and $P < 0.0001$), but there was no significant difference in the IVM (+) group (Figure 6(G,H)). No changes were observed in IL-12 expression (Figure 6(I,J)). Interestingly, co-culturing of HD11 cells with *A. galli* EVs in the range of approximately 1–100 EVs per host cell was also shown to increase phagocytosis of fluorescent targets in a small data set (Supplementary Fig 2).

Discussion

Comprehensive understanding of host–pathogen interactions and communication between parasitic worms and chickens are vital in finding solutions to control and treat the infections. Thus, the present study presents the observed evidence of immunomodulatory potential of excretory-secretory products and EVs derived from the nematode *A. galli*. By examining their interactions with avian immune cells, specifically T-cells and HD11 macrophage-like cells, and assessing the impact of IVM treatment on these interactions, our findings provide valuable insights into host–parasite dynamics and the modulation of immune responses by the *A. galli* parasitic nematodes.

Previous studies have demonstrated that nematodes possess the ability to modulate host immune responses, enabling their persistence and replication within the host. At the initial phase of the infection, it is hypothesized that early host–pathogen communication facilitates the penetration and invasion of the pathogen by weakening or evading the innate and humoral immunity of host. However, in the current study, we focused on ES/EVs derived from adult *A. galli* worms, as these represent the chronic stage of infection, during which prolonged host–parasite interactions occur. Additionally, adult worms provide a reliable and abundant source of ES/EVs, addressing the technical challenges of obtaining sufficient quantities from larvae due to their smaller size and shorter lifespan. The composition and quantity of ES/EVs can vary across life stages. The chosen approach should be complemented with studies on early-stage immune activation, but it offers insights into mechanisms of sustained immune modulation during long-term infections. Recent evidence suggests that excretory-secretory products released by the nematodes consist of molecules such as lipids, glycans, proteins, and RNA which play a significant role in modulating host immunity (Cooper & Eleftherianos, 2016; White, McManus *et al.*, 2020a; Yan, 2025). In this study, we observed the activation and proliferation of peripheral blood T-cells following treatment with ES products collected from *A. galli* *in vitro* culture after 24 h. Specifically, the suppression of T-cell activation, including CD25+ and CD57+ cell frequencies, along with reduced blast formation in both CD4+ and CD8+ T-cells exposed to nematode ES products, suggests that *A. galli* may actively interfere with the host's adaptive immune system. Such interference suppresses or modulates T-cell-mediated immune responses may contribute to nematode immune evasion. In sum, our findings confirm that *A. galli*-derived ES products have the capacity to modulate and suppress host immune T-cell responses.

Figure 6. Expression of selected cytokines in LPS-activated macrophages in the presence of different numbers of *A. galli* nematode EVs/particles enriched from Ivermectin treated and non-treated nematode culture supernatant. (A) IL-10 expression after treatment with EVs enriched from IVM (–) culture supernatant, (B) IL-10 expression after treatment with EVs enriched from IVM + culture supernatant, (C) iNOS expression after treatment with EVs enriched from IVM (–) culture supernatant, (D) iNOS expression after treatment with EVs enriched from IVM (+) culture supernatant, (E) IL-1β expression after treatment with EVs enriched from IVM (–) culture supernatant, (F) IL-1β expression after treatment with EVs enriched from IVM (+) culture supernatant, (G) IL-8 expression after treatment with EVs enriched from IVM (–) culture supernatant, (H) IL-8 expression after treatment with EVs enriched from IVM (+) culture supernatant, (I) IL-12 expression after treatment with EVs enriched from IVM (–) culture supernatant, (J) IL-12 expression after treatment with EVs enriched from IVM (+) culture supernatant (mean ± standard error, * = $P < 0.05$ IVM (–) groups compared to their control group, and # = $P < 0.05$ IVM (+) groups compared to their control group).

Figure 6. Continued.

The ES products from worms treated with IVM did not significantly affect the frequencies of CD4+CD25+ and CD4+CD57+ or blast transformed cells. These findings suggest that IVM treatment may reduce or inhibit the ability of *A. galli* to secrete components that modulate host immunity, potentially allowing the host immune system to effectively detect and combat the parasite.

Macrophages are key innate immune cells responsible for pathogen recognition, phagocytosis, and initiating inflammatory responses, making them a vital component of the host's defence against infections, including nematode infections. A previous study by van den Biggelaar *et al.* (2020) highlights the

suitability of the HD11 cell line as an *in vitro* model to study the innate immune responses of chickens. In our study, we examined the impact of ES products from *A. galli* on macrophage activity, and our findings reveal that these ES products significantly modulate macrophage function. Our results demonstrated that the NO production and MRC1L-B expression were increased in LPS-activated HD11 cells treated with both IVM (+) and IVM (-) spent media.

The measurement of NO production by HD11 cells is widely used as a valuable biomarker for the *in vitro* assessment of innate immune responses in chickens and also employed as a bioindicator for evaluating batch-to-batch consistency in vaccine production

(van den Biggelaar *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, the surface expression of MRC1L-B and MHC-II in macrophages serves as a reliable indicator of macrophage function (Staines *et al.*, 2014). Interestingly, we observed a significant increase in NO production and MRC1L-B expression in HD11 cells treated with ES products, further suggesting that *A. galli* secretes factors capable of modulating host immune responses. However, high NO production and MRC1L-B expression were significantly higher at both medium and high concentrations of IVM (-) spent media (18×, 54×, and 162× dilutions), whereas the IVM (+) group displayed notable increases only at higher concentrations (18× and 54× dilutions). These findings indicate that immune-modulating components in the ES product collected from the IVM (+) group may be less potent compared to the IVM (-) group. Thus, it can be postulated that IVM may selectively inhibit the secretion of nematode-derived proteins or small molecules that strongly activate immune responses, such as those mimicking pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) or modulating inflammatory pathways. This highlights the potential role of IVM in mitigating the immunomodulatory effects of *A. galli* ES products.

These findings are well aligned with the previous studies that confirm the ability of IVM to inhibit the capacity of the nematodes to suppress host immune responses (Laing *et al.*, 2017; Martin *et al.*, 2021). However, IVM does not have the potential to completely abolish the immunomodulatory effects of nematode ES. The phagocytosis data further demonstrate a concentration-dependent effect, in which highly diluted IVM (+) spent media enhances macrophage phagocytic activity, while higher concentrations suppress it, indicating that nematode factors retain immunosuppressive potency at higher secretion. Moreover, our findings highlight that while IVM weakens nematode-mediated suppression of innate immunity, it is insufficient to fully counteract their immunomodulatory mechanisms, particularly those targeting adaptive immune functions. This underscores the complexity of host-nematode interactions and the limitations of IVM in completely restoring immune functionality.

EVs are recognized as cargo carriers, playing a significant role in host-pathogen interactions (Rooney *et al.*, 2022). Previous studies suggest that the ES products released by nematodes contain biological molecules capable of inducing immunomodulation in the host (Cooper & Eleftherianos, 2016). In this study, we investigated the role of *A. galli* EVs in modulating host immunity and examined the impact of IVM on EV secretion by nematodes. Furthermore, we investigated how IVM treatment alters the immunomodulatory properties of EVs, which are released by nematodes treated with and without IVM. Interestingly, there are no previous reports on the enrichment

of EVs specifically from *A. galli* nematodes. We successfully enriched nematode-derived EVs from ES collected from *in vitro* nematode cultures by employing differential centrifugation and SEC with minor modifications. Combining two or more EV enrichment techniques can improve the purity of EVs (Prasadani *et al.*, 2024; Premathilaka *et al.*, 2025). The size distribution of the enriched nanoparticles indicated that they align within the identical range for EVs. TEM analysis further confirmed the presence of EVs, revealing a double-membrane EV population with the typical shape and structure characteristic of EVs (Welsh *et al.*, 2024). Both NTA and TEM data showed that the enriched samples contained EVs in different sizes, highlighting the heterogeneity of EVs secreted by nematodes. Protein analysis assays revealed minimal soluble protein contamination in the EV-enriched fractions, while TEM images showed the presence of minimal artefacts, supporting the purity of the samples. Based on these findings, we propose that our optimized method is effective for enriching EVs from *in vitro* *A. galli* cultures with minimal contaminants. This method provides a robust foundation for future studies on the role of *A. galli* EVs in host-pathogen interactions and the impact of IVM on EV-mediated immunomodulation. Further EV cargo characterization, using transcriptomics and proteomics, will help us gain an in-depth understanding of the *A. galli* EVs that may support the immunomodulatory effects observed in the present study.

Previous studies have explained that the treatment with IVM can inhibit the secretion of EVs by nematodes (Loghry *et al.*, 2020). Our experimental findings confirmed that IVM treatment significantly reduces the release of EVs by *A. galli* nematodes. This reduction highlights the ability of IVM to disrupt host-pathogen communication, and it can lead to preventing the immunomodulation induced by the pathogen through EV-mediated mechanisms. As illustrated in Figure 4, IVM treatment effectively reduces the secretion of EVs from *in vitro* cultured *A. galli* worms. However, the treatment does not alter the size distribution of the EV population.

Helminth-derived EVs are recognized as cargo carriers that transport molecules with the ability to modulate host immunity. Particularly, proteins, lipids and RNA cargo within nematode-derived EVs are well-documented for their crucial role in host immune modulation (Drurey & Maizels, 2021). To investigate the involvement of *A. galli*-derived EVs in the immunomodulation of chickens, we examined the changes in gene expression of selected cytokines in LPS-activated macrophages. Further studies on EV effects on macrophage phagocytosis and T-cell proliferation are warranted. However, large amounts of isolated EVs are needed. Hence, in this study we choose to focus on a single functional assay as the amount of purified

EVs was a limitation under batch culture and SEC method. A significant upregulation of the immunoregulatory cytokine IL-10 was observed in macrophages treated with nematode-derived EVs, particularly at higher particle numbers. This suggests that nematode EVs may carry molecular components capable of promoting an anti-inflammatory response, potentially contributing to immune evasion. By suppressing pro-inflammatory cytokine production of the host, pathogens gain the ability to evade innate immune clearance and establish persistent infections (Subramanian Iyer & Cheng, 2012; Kessler *et al.*, 2017). Notably, the IVM(-) group exhibited a consistently higher IL-10 expression compared to the IVM(+) group. Hence, EVs derived from nematodes not treated with IVM possess more potent immunoregulatory capabilities, potentially due to a more diverse or active molecular cargo loading *in vivo* compared to EVs from IVM-treated worms. Moreover, IVM treatment appears to reduce the immunomodulatory capacity of EVs, likely by altering the composition or function of their cargo. An earlier study on *Dirofilaria immitis* has also suggested that macrocyclic lactones, such as IVM, disrupt the parasite's ability to evade the host's innate immune system (Vatta *et al.*, 2014).

Our data clearly highlight the presence and interplay between parasite-derived EVs and host immune cells. Furthermore, our findings explain that nematode-derived EVs play a pivotal role in modulating host immunity, serving as early communication molecules that enable parasites to evade host innate immunity, facilitating their invasion and persistence within the host. The observed differences in gene expression suggest that IVM treatment may alter the cargo composition of nematode EVs, potentially weakening their immunomodulatory capabilities. Moreover, IVM treatment also significantly reduces the production of EVs by *A. galli* nematodes and this reduction further explains the role of IVM in interfering with nematode-driven immune modulation and emphasizes its potential in controlling parasitic infections by targeting EV secretion. Additionally, the findings underscore the potential for targeting parasite EVs as part of integrated control strategies and provide a foundation for further exploration of their roles in host-parasite interactions.

To examine the alteration of the molecular composition of EV-associated cargo during IVM treatment, we assessed the metabolic compositions of EVs enriched from IVM (+) and IVM (-) nematode cultures using FTIR. Significant metabolic alterations were observed in EVs of *A. galli* following IVM treatment, as evidenced by shifts in protein and polysaccharide regions. Notable changes in the amide I (1650 cm^{-1}) and amide II (1545 cm^{-1}) bands, corresponding to C=O stretching vibrations and peptide bond structures, indicate modifications in protein

content and backbone structure. Additionally, alterations in the polysaccharide-associated regions suggest disrupted glycosylation pathways and variations in glycoprotein cargo. Collectively, these spectral variations highlight the influence of IVM on the molecular composition and metabolic functionality of EVs, potentially impacting the parasite's physiology and host interactions. Interestingly, use of FTIR brings out a new perspective in the future to identify the batch-to-batch variation during EV enrichment to avoid heterogeneity of the treatments.

In this study, we employed an *in vitro* model to investigate the immunomodulatory properties of *A. galli* ES/EVs and to study the impact of IVM on these interactions. While *in vitro* models provide a controlled environment to unravel specific mechanisms, they inherently lack the complexity of *in vivo* conditions. For instance, the immune interactions observed *in vitro* do not account for the systemic immune responses or the influence of other host tissues and microbiota present in a natural host environment. These factors could significantly influence host-parasite dynamics, potentially resulting in differences in the immunomodulatory effects and the impact of IVM on host-pathogen interactions *in vivo* compared to our *in vitro* observations. However, this model provides a valuable foundation for understanding the molecular mechanisms underlying *A. galli*-mediated immune modulation and the effects of IVM.

In conclusion, ES products of *A. galli* impart notable immunomodulatory effects, influencing host immune responses. Our findings also demonstrate the first evidence that *A. galli* ES contain EVs that can promote host immune modulation. Thus, the current study provides fundamental information for developing precise strategies that utilize EVs as diagnostic tools or targets for therapeutic development. Future studies are required to study the EV cargo composition and the molecular mechanisms driving EV-mediated immune modulation and to investigate their potential applications in managing parasitic infections in both veterinary and human contexts.

Ethics statement

The experiments involving birds were conducted according to Danish legislation governing animal experimentation (Law no. 382, 10 June 1987; Acts 739, 6 December 1988; and Act 333, 19 May 1990) and were approved by the Danish Animal Experiments Inspectorate (Animal license no. 2022-15-0201-01222).

Authors' contributions

Conceptualization, S.K., A.F., and T.S.D.; Data curation, C.P., A.S.F., K.P., R.K., and T.S.D.; Formal

analysis, C.P., A.S.F., K.P., and T.S.D.; Funding acquisition, S.K., A.F., and T.S.D.; Investigation, C.P., A.S.F., K.P., R.K., S.K., A.F., and T.S.D.; Methodology, C.P., A.S.F., K.P., R.K., A.A., S.K., A.F., and T.S.D.; Project administration, S.K., A.F. and T.S.D.; Resources, S.K., A.F. and T.S.D.; Software, C.P., A.S.F., K.P., and R.K.; Supervision, R.K., S.K., A.F., and T.S.D.; Validation, C.P., A.S.F., K.P., R.K., S.K., A.F., and T.S.D.; Visualization, C.P., A.S.F., and A.A.; Writing – original draft, C.P.; Writing – review and editing, C.P., A.S.F., K.P., R.K., S.K., A.F., and T.S.D. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author [T.S.D.], upon reasonable request.

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